

PROJECT AND RESEARCH ACTIVITIES IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract

The relevance of this work to ensure the formation of foreign language competence and the development of such qualities of a student's personality as a culture of communication, the ability to work in collaboration, the ability and readiness for further self-education with its help in various fields of knowledge allows - design and research activities. The central figure in the process of this activity is the personality of the student, who has the opportunity to interact with other participants in the educational process, to develop comprehensively and freely creatively, to master the necessary competencies.

Keywords: project and research, organization, English, project activity, training.

Introduction

The high level of innovation, the speed of changes taking place in society, the "explosion of information" itself lead to an acceleration of the aging process of knowledge. Hence the need for the development of a new type of employee. What qualities are necessary for a modern graduate? Different people answer this question in different ways. · Someone talks about deep and solid knowledge, · others - about education, · others - about the development of intellectual and creative forces of children, their ability to learn, the formation of the ability to self-development... However, everyone always agrees that the school should help every child to become happy: to find their place in life, to make true friends, to build a family, to realize themselves in their chosen profession. The understanding of this was formed in the culture hundreds of years ago. "The main goal of the educator," A. Disterveg believed, "should be the development of amateur activity, thanks to which a person can subsequently become the manager of his fate, the continuer of the education of his life..." P.F. Kapterev, D.I. Pisarev, K.D. Ushinsky, L.N. Tolstoy, A.N. Leontiev, P.Ya. Galperin, V.V. wrote about it. Davydov, L.V. Zankov and many other famous teachers and psychologists in our country and abroad. The analysis of the historical development of the educational sphere shows that the requirements for the training of graduates from the society have changed. Today, the social order of society for education is radically different from the previous one. It is not the knowledge itself that becomes necessary, but knowledge about how and where to apply it. In the competence paradigm, education aims to master a set of competencies necessary for successful adaptation in an ever-changing modern society.[1]

Materials and types of research

The objectives of this study are: development and self-development of the personality of students through their involvement in project and research activities in English lessons. The organization of educational activities in such a way that students have formed the needs for the implementation of creative transformation of educational material in order to acquire new knowledge.

Research results

The application of the project methodology increases the interest of students in learning English and contributes to the development of internal motivation by transferring the center of the learning process from the teacher to the student. I believe that positive motivation is the key to successful learning of a foreign language.

The use of design and research activities increases the effectiveness of teaching. The results of observations showed that all students work more actively in the classroom: both "weak" and "strong". For underachieving children, there is an opportunity to move forward in obtaining new knowledge. For the "strong" - an opportunity to expand their knowledge using additional literature on the subject. The teacher has the opportunity to pay attention to both "weak" and "strong" students in the lesson. The change of activities, as well as the fulfillment of tasks by students of various levels of complexity make the lesson interesting, eliminate the psychological burden, allow the children to realize themselves as much as possible in the classroom and in extracurricular activities[1].

Project activity is one of the most important areas of personality-oriented learning. The task of the teacher in this process is to identify the selectivity of the student to the content, type, form of educational material, the process of self-realization and the type of activity [1, p. 6].

Modern children learn computer technology very quickly. The task of teachers is to direct this rapidly growing potential to the use of PCs in the classroom, as well as in preparation for classes. This will help students realize all their opportunities in their future profession, because computerization will only gain momentum. The value of this method is that the student is personally interested in this activity. Students can work individually or in groups, but this does not negate the fact that they all want to reveal their topic in full. Only personal interest in the project can help a child achieve high results. No less significant is the fact that children are expanding the ways of working with information sources: search, collection and analysis of the infor-

mation received, presentation and transmission of information, modeling, design, reflection. And most importantly, the child acquires the most important self—learning skills. This will help him in becoming a full-fledged personality. Our main goal is to show students how important critical thinking and orientation in information is. They should be able to navigate the information space, reflect and analyze based on real facts, draw conclusions that they can justify themselves, make independent decisions and be responsible for them, as well as be able to work in a team, skillfully distributing roles and positions. [3] Classical methods of teaching English are often based on a "dry" presentation of material that is difficult for students to perceive, which completely discourages children from learning and memorizing something new. The same cannot be said about project activities. It provides an opportunity for students to study the topic more and more deeply, significantly expands their general horizons, teaches them to communicate and build their thoughts, and much more. All this serves a deeper understanding of the role of our country in an interdependent world, the formation of a civic position and the maximum development of individual abilities of students. Behind each project there is a huge work of students, which will not be in vain for them, but will give them the opportunity to look at themselves in a new way.

For a teacher, project activity is a way of organizing work with different groups of students, which in turn means the path of advancement of each student from a lower to a higher level of learning (from simple reproduction and repetition to creativity). At the beginning of the process, students usually form small groups where everyone has their own task and is responsible for it. Distributing roles in the group, some skills are mainly taken into account: logical reasoning, drawing conclusions, design of project work. Most often, students themselves cope with the task of dividing into groups, but the teacher always closely monitors this process so that no one is left deprived [2, p. 15]. In the process of work, students are engaged in creating multimedia presentations in English, which in turn implies a creative approach to this type of activity. Secondary school students must own Microsoft Word, Microsoft Power Point. Using these programs.

Project and research activity is the activity of designing one's own research, involving the allocation of goals and objectives, principles of selection of methods, planning the course of research, determining the expected results, evaluating the feasibility of research, determining the necessary resources. It is the organizational framework of the study.

Having comprehended in more detail and in detail the ideas of design and research activities, I came to the conclusion that it more fully corresponds to my pedagogical principles:

- a systematic approach to planning and studying the material;
- inclusion in the system of lessons of all links of the cognitive process;
- early presentation of requirements for the final result of training;

- giving the student the opportunity to work at an individual pace;
- increasing the share of independent work on obtaining and comprehending educational information at different stages of the lesson;
- use of individual, pair and group work.

I believe that the positive motivation for using this activity lies in the fact that it combines education and upbringing into a holistic process of developing a creative personality and makes it possible for students to interactively engage in the educational process.

3. The leading pedagogical idea.

Project and research activity is humanistic, because the child in it is not an object of learning, but a subject. Development in the process of independent work gives a greater result than attempts to instill the necessary skills and abilities "from above". Moreover, subject-subject relations are established in the relationship between the student and the teacher, where the teacher is a partner in teaching, and not a "giver" of knowledge. The student learns by himself, and the teacher only carries out motivational management of his teaching. The student is free, his interests are not infringed, the results of the work are based primarily on his self-esteem. [4]

Consequently, design and research activity is a personality-oriented activity, where the personality of the child is at the center of the educational system, it is also the main goal of the educational system. The strength and awareness of mastering the material, the development of intelligence also depends on the degree of independence of the student in operating with educational material.

Design and research work prepares students for independence, develops an active life position.

1. The design and research activities combine new approaches to learning and traditions accumulated since the emergence of the usual combined lesson.

2. Design and research activity helps to avoid shock among students, because constant reflection gives information to the teacher about the state of the educational process.

3. It is assumed that the organization of educational activities in which the student himself operates with the educational content, which, of course, leads to a more solid and conscious assimilation of the material.

4. Design and research activity of students is one of the progressive forms of education in a modern school. It allows you to fully identify and develop both intellectual and creative abilities of children.

5. In the process of project and research activities, students develop the following qualities: the ability to organize their work, the skills and knowledge of a research nature, the ability to work with information, the ability to present the result of their work.

Thus, the design and research activity is not limited to the acquisition of certain knowledge, skills and abilities by students, but goes to the practical actions of students, affecting their emotional sphere, thereby increasing the motivation of students to the subject, developing their intellectual and personal qualities. And since the student performs self-valuable educational ac-

tivity, he develops himself, expresses himself as a person, which is of great importance in increasing his self-esteem. It can be concluded that in the process of design and research activities, students develop the following qualities:

1. The ability to organize their work (workplace organization, work planning).
2. Skills and knowledge of a research nature (choosing a research topic, goal setting as a stage of activity, the ability to build a research structure, research methods, general logical methods, information retrieval).
3. The ability to work with information (types of information, sources of information, scientific text, term, concept, semantic parts of the text: paragraphs, chapters, paragraphs, the ability to highlight the main thing, summary, quote, link, definition plan, conclusion, formulation of conclusions, logic of presentation, summary, methods of taking notes, conventional signs, proof: arguments, facts, introduction and conclusion).
4. The ability to present the result of their work (forms of presentation of results, forms of scientific meetings, requirements for the report, the speaker's speech).

Project research activity is understood by me not only in the specific organizational framework of working on a given problem and writing a research paper to students, but more broadly. Using the words of S.L. Rubinstein, I adhere to the position that teaching in general is "a joint study conducted by a teacher and a student." Thus, the task of the teacher is understood in the creation of a hypothetical-projective model for the formation of a developing environment for students (the context of development). [5] It is the teacher who sets the forms and conditions of research activity, thanks to which the student forms an internal motivation to approach any problem that arises before him (both scientific and everyday) from a research, creative position. It follows from this that one of the most significant tasks is to resolve the issue of ways to form internal motivation. The scientific approach to the research process in pedagogical practice requires the implementation of a number of principles, in particular:

- the principle of naturalness (the problem should not be far-fetched, but real, the interest should not be artificial, but real, etc.);
- the principle of awareness (both problems, goals and objectives, and the course of research and its results);
- the principle of self-activity (a child can master the course of research only through living it, that is, through his own experience);
- the principle of visibility (existing in pedagogy since Ya.A. Komensky and developed by I.G. Pestalozzi and J.-J. Rousseau. It can be implemented most well in a field study, where a child studies the world not only from books, but what it really is);
- the principle of cultural conformity (coming from F.V.A. Disterweg and developed in our country by K.D. Ushinsky, P.F. Kapterev and many others. It is important to take into account the tradition of worldview that exists in this culture; the tradition of in-

teraction that It is important to take into account the tradition of worldview that exists in this culture; the tradition of interaction that exists.

Research activity is based on the principles of design (Shchedrovitsky G.P., Alekseev N.G.), where a research project is a driving form of building interpersonal interaction between a researcher and a supervisor, during which the cultural values of the scientific community are broadcast. Education, therefore, becomes productive, since there is a real way out in a completed and formalized research work as a result. In this case, the product has rather not material, but intellectual and personal value, becoming significant for the creator of this product (student). In addition, a research project is not only a form, a means and a principle of organizing cultural interaction, but also a motive for this activity.

Thus, it is necessary to talk about the possibility and reasonableness of using research activities as a form of organizing interpersonal interaction between a teacher and a student, during which cultural traditions of scientific knowledge are broadcast. This form is consonant with the peculiarities of adolescence and adolescent subculture, organizationally contributing to the resolution of a number of tasks in the development of a teenager's personality and his entry into the cultural space.

I define the design and research activity of students as a creative process of joint activity of two subjects (a teacher and a student) to find a solution to the unknown, during which cultural values are transmitted between them, the result of which is the formation of a worldview. As a teacher in this case, I act as an organizer of the form and conditions of project and research activities, thanks to which the student forms an internal motivation to approach any scientific or life problem that arises in front of him from a research, creative position. [6]

In addition, the design and research activity successfully combines the principles of three main approaches:

- 1) competence-based approach to learning
- 2) personality-oriented learning
- 3) technology of developing learning

Design and research activity allows you to form key competencies, because students work independently most of the time, learn planning, organization, self-control and evaluation of their actions, communication and activities in general. In the process of working with projects, the following are formed:

- value-semantic competence (defines the scope of the student's worldview related to his value orientations, his ability to see and understand the world around him).
- general cultural competence (reflects the range of issues in relation to which the student should be well aware). For example, fundamental achievements in the field of English and their practical significance.
- educational and cognitive competence (includes elements of logical, general educational activities. This includes knowledge and skills in comparison, classification of objects according to one or more criteria, solving educational problems according to given algorithms, creative solution of practical tasks).

- information competence (forms the ability to independently search and analyze the necessary information)

- communicative competence (includes knowledge of ways to interact with other people, group work skills, knowledge of various social roles in the team)

The teacher is assigned a managerial role in the organization of the educational process.

In this regard, the following management principles should be listed:

1) differentiated approach to students in compliance with the feasibility of educational tasks;

2) a systematic increase in intellectual loads and a consistent transition to more incomplete instructions for performing independent work;

3) gradual separation of the teacher and his occupation of the position of a passive observer of the process;

4) the transition from teacher control to self-control.

It follows from this that one of the most significant tasks is to resolve the question of how to form internal motivation, that is, translating the external need to search for the unknown into an internal need. The organization of independent cognitive activity of students in the classroom is an important condition for personality-oriented learning.

Principles of personality-oriented learning implemented using project-based research training:

Individualization is the creation of a multi-level training system that takes into account the individual characteristics of students and provides everyone with the opportunity to maximize their abilities.

The contextual approach is subordination of the content and logic of studying educational material of general education disciplines to the interests of future professional activity, as a result of which learning acquires a conscious, substantive, contextual character, contributing to the strengthening of cognitive interest and cognitive activity. [7]

The development of cooperation is a practical awareness of the need to switch to the principles of trust and mutual assistance. Providing assistance to students in organizing their educational activities in combination with maintaining a demanding attitude to its effectiveness. The development of respect, trust in the student, with the provision of opportunities for him to show independence, initiative and individual responsibility for the result.

New principles of personality-oriented education, individual approach, subjectivity in teaching require such teaching methods that provide:

- active, independent and initiative position of students in teaching;

- development, first of all, of general academic skills: research, reflexive, self-assessment;

- the formation of not just skills, but competencies, i.e. skills directly related to the experience of their application in practice;

- priority targeting of the development of cognitive interest of students;

- implementation of the principle of the connection of learning with life

The third component of my experience is the technology of developmental learning. When preparing for lessons, I rely on the basic principles of developmental learning. Namely:

- Putting at the forefront of the pedagogical process the development of the student's personality as a guarantee of his successful self-realization, the direct participation of the student in the development of strategies and tactics of educational activities;

- Development of research activities, assistance in mastering the algorithm of self-knowledge and organization of various activities;

- Creating a comfortable atmosphere of the lesson, allowing to identify the creative abilities of the individual, to promote their development and manifestation, to track personal results in the learning process, including the intermediate result

Thus, all three of these technologies put forward principles that contribute to the development of an active, socially adapted and self-developing personality. [8]

So, from the point of view of modernization of education, design and research activity of students as a technology based on design processes is an important component of the system of productive education and represents a non-standard, non-traditional way of organizing educational processes through active methods of action (planning, forecasting, analysis, synthesis) aimed at implementing a personality-oriented approach. Designing helps students to realize the role of knowledge in life and learning – knowledge ceases to be a goal, but becomes a means in genuine education. By the end of such training, children are able to choose the most appropriate form of continuing education. This is how the education system is built in the leading countries of the world, which reflects the humanistic direction in pedagogy. The use of design and research activities in the classroom

I believe that the educational process should ideally simulate the process of scientific research, the search for new knowledge. Thus, my work in the lesson is built taking into account the age needs and capabilities of the child, as well as didactic considerations and represents the following structure by class.

First of all, I tried to organize the independent work of schoolchildren in the classroom. These were mostly short-term projects that fit into the lesson. At the initial stage, children are trained in joint creative and research activities. In elementary school, albums are created-chronicles of the family, class, which can then be collected into one large album or placed on one large stand. Children compose thematic dictionaries, draw filmstrips. Another form of work in the classroom where the use of research activities is possible is the development of phonetic skills, which consists in training the correct pronunciation of sounds, and also the rules of reading English vowels are studied. Initially, students are asked to recall letters and sounds, They must name these letters, identify the sounds they transmit and give examples of words where they are used. In the course of such work, students can use the media

objects presented on the slides. At the end of the research work with English letters and sounds, students under my guidance test themselves with the help of the author's game program "Rules for reading English vowels".

In grades 5-6, the main direction of work is Self-education. "Do it yourself." Working with children of this age, I orient them to acquire positive personality traits. At the same time, I use the following tasks: making fairy tales on the topic of the lesson, poems, stories, expressing the topic through a photograph, drawing. In grades 5, short-term practice-oriented monoprojects are carried out, which is explained by the concreteness of children's thinking. By students of grades 5, projects were carried out on the topics: "My family", "My house", "My friend", "Daily routine", "Letter to an English friend", "New Year's card". These are creative projects, many guys used a computer when doing projects. Fifth grade students made creative presentations about themselves on the topics covered, using their photos, pictures, keywords, phrases that help them tell. Such performances arouse great interest of classmates and a lot of questions, which is a good incentive to talk in the language. I also form students' research skills by working with texts. While working with the text, students often encounter phrases like "Buy time", "The hands of the clock", etc. Each individual word in the examples given is well known to schoolchildren, but the phrases themselves can cause some difficulties in translation. There is a need for some kind of analytical work. [9]

1. Buy – buy time – time - words from the active dictionary.

2. The hypothesis is expressed that the phrase buy time is the equivalent of a stable expression from the Russian language "to win time".

3. Let's check if this translation fits the context: "Well, yes...I think it is... - I said just to buy time (Okay, yes... I suppose it is... - I said, just to buy time)". The hypothesis turned out to be correct. In this case, the simplest search forms are used, but the skills of research work are acquired gradually. Students are also gradually learning to work with language units.

One more example should be given when it is important not so much the ability to work with a dictionary, but to apply elements of the analysis of research work.

There is a sentence in the text:

"Lend me your ear, he said trying to turn in my direction."

In this case, the expression Lend me your ear is not entirely clear. Reasoning:

land – lend, lend

Ear – ear;

The expression "borrow an ear" is likely to lead the guys into confusion, additional work with the dictionary will be required. The English-English dictionary gives several examples with this expression, here is one of them: "Are you anywhere in a hurry? – Mag took me by the sleeve ... I need to tell you something, lend me your ear, please (Are you in a hurry? – asked Meg I need to tell you something, can I have your attention, please?)". From this context, the meaning of the desired phrase becomes clearer. We train not only the language

guess, but also the ability to prove the initial assumption. [10]

Research activities in English lessons are applicable, of course, and when introducing new grammatical rules. This could not be more justified for a number of reasons. The first reason is psychological. It is well known that the material that was extracted by logical reasoning and independent conclusions is best remembered. The second reason is linguistic. Russian schoolchildren, while learning English, encounter a number of grammatical structures, which have no analogue in the Russian language: 12 tenses of the English verb, a complex system of prepositions and some others. Research work just helps to overcome some of the inevitable difficulties in learning a language.

Research work begins already when studying the simplest grammatical constructions. For example, the present simple tense of the verb to be (to be).

- I am a teacher.
- He is a doctor.
- She is a nurse.
- They are pupils.
- We are pilots.
- You are my friend.
- It is a cat.

The analysis of these sentences leads students to the conclusion that the verb to be in the present simple tense has 3 forms – am, is, are. Further analysis of the sentences allows you to make the following table, according to the person / number of the verb:

- I – am
- He / She / It – is
- They / We / You – are

Here is another example of using search forms in an English lesson.

When introducing the topic Present Simple Tense (simple present tense), I build my work as follows:

1. First, I ask students to compare sentences denoting everyday activities (go to work, clean flat, go in for sport, etc., and pictures denoting these actions:

Mary goes to work by car every day (Mary goes to work by car).

Steve and Robby clean their flat every weekend (Steve and Robby clean

the apartment on weekends).

Liz plays volleyball twice a week (Liz plays volleyball twice a week).

I usually come to school at 8 o'clock (I usually come to school at 8 o'clock), etc.

At this stage, the language guess works.

2. Then the guys get the task: to pick up the continuation of the existing sentences, choosing from the ones proposed by the teacher that fit the original sentence both in meaning and grammatically. For example:

Marry goes to work by car every day.

- but sometimes takes a bus.

- and never come late.

By reasoning and comparisons, we hypothesize that the correct option is the first sentence. Check: in all sentences in which the verb is in the 3rd person, it has the ending -s, the verb takes also has the ending – s. Therefore, this is really the correct option. We also select the appropriate endings for all sentences. After

completing the task, we conclude that the verb in the present simple tense in the singular of the third person will have the ending – s. [11]

My role in introducing new material is to guide the work of students, to help in the search for the right result. Students themselves extract the necessary information, analyze the results obtained, formulate rules, respectively, it is easier to remember them, and also acquire such important skills as the ability to identify the main thing, compare, find analogies and draw conclusions.

Various forms of research activity can be used even at the initial stage of language learning with children aged 8-12 years when mastering grammatical material, making such work into an exciting game. I also use such tasks at later stages of training to master the subtleties of the language. For example, when studying phrasal verbs, stable expressions, idioms – in the case when you need to work with a dictionary, analyze the already existing knowledge of both the native and the language being studied. For example, the effective use of research in the study of the following topics:

- "Verb forms to be in the present tense" (Beginner level);
- "Past tense ending –ed for regular verbs, past tense forms of irregular verbs" (Beginner/Elementary level);
- Subjunctive mood 0, 1, 2, 3 types (Pre-Intermediate level);
- "Future Simple Time" (Beginner/ Elementary level);
- Phrasal verbs (level (level Pre-Intermediate, Intermediate, Upper- Intermediate). [12]

In the 7th grade – the direction of the work "Teach yourself to learn". "Self-education". For this age, I select tasks that develop the student's skills and abilities that increase interest in learning. Drafting projects on the topic, using itinerary sheets, presentations, slide films, messages and reports, drawing up comparative characteristics. At the second stage of training, due to the increase in the level of creativity, interest in literary and creative mono-projects increases. There is a new, more complex type of project — informational, which allows us to conclude that the level of language competence of students is increasing. Work continues on the information type of the project. The level of language competence increases, analytical, associative and system thinking, combinatorial skills develop. Interdisciplinary connections are being strengthened, the general outlook is expanding. The information project acquires an interdisciplinary character. When choosing the topic of an abstract or research paper, students are guided by their desires and interests. At the end of the work, students submit creative reports. The forms can be different: the publication of a newspaper, a school magazine, the design of an exhibition, a creative report on an experiment, the defense of an abstract or research paper. [13]

Conclusion

Project and research activities are modern, productive and personality-oriented, allowing students to better assimilate the material of the program. Practice shows that the effectiveness of the learning process is

much higher if the student masters the techniques of self-education. After all, the main task of a teacher is to teach his wards to independently acquire knowledge.

The role of the teacher in such a lesson is reduced to managing the work of schoolchildren, to correcting ways to solve the tasks set.

The use of design and research activities increases the effectiveness of teaching. The results of observations showed that all students work more actively in the classroom: both "weak" and "strong". For underachieving children, there is an opportunity to move forward in obtaining new knowledge. For the "strong" - an opportunity to expand their knowledge using additional literature on the subject. The teacher has the opportunity to pay attention to both "weak" and "strong" students in the lesson. The change of activities, as well as the fulfillment of tasks by students of various levels of complexity make the lesson interesting, eliminate the psychological burden, allow the children to realize themselves as much as possible in the classroom and in extracurricular activities.

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